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PETITION TO PARLIAMENT ON THE ISSUE OF LBGTQI+ FROM APOSTLE DR. ALEX OFOSU, FORMER GENERAL SECRETARY OF THE APOSTOLIC CHURCH-GHANA

CULTURE

Anthropologists and other behavioural scientist have expressed that culture is the full range of learned human behaviour patterns. Culture is that complex whole including knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, customs, and any other abilities and habits acquired by people as members of society”.¹

Noticeably, we live, behave and teach what we have been taught. It is imperative to realize that our values and emotions, our underlying prejudices, attitudes, and drives would over a time shape any person who enters into a particular community like any one of us.

No doubt that within the cultural context of our early beginnings as a people, our leaders seemed to have understood this principle quite clearly. Our forefather’s communication policy of storytelling and parables moved their audience towards a certain orientation.

As a people, we need to make every effort to understand and adopt indigenous cultural norms for our wellbeing. But in doing that, there are times we also need to reject certain cultural norms which conflict with our belief.

¹ Lutzbetak, J. L., ‘The Church and Cultures, New Perspectives in Missiological Anthropology’ Orbis Books, 1988), page, 134

GENDER

An attempt by a certain school of thoughts has tried to redefine the meaning of the word 'gender.' To this school of thoughts, the contemporary meaning of gender refers to one's sense of who one is as a person. Gender is not the same as one's physical characteristics such as genes and hormones found in persons. They maintain that gender identity and expression occur along a broad spectrum that obviously is not restricted to two binary alternatives, such as a woman/man or boy/girl. Many at times, identifying one's gender could be more diverse than simply seeing one's self as a male or female. People sometimes express their gender in different ways.

Again, this school of thoughts has maintained that our everyday life is entirely driven by communication; the language that we speak. This implies that communication, to be effective, must have an exchange of ideas taking cognizance of our gender identities and peculiarities. It is important that we look for the needs of all categories of people. Look for barriers, develop or change policies and procedures that affect the wellbeing of persons. This will help and make sure that the rights of all genders are treated with dignity and respect and enjoy equal rights. It is imperative, therefore, to avoid using 'he' or 'she' as a universal pronoun as well as using binary alternatives such as 'he' or 'she' in our everyday language even as we communicate with ourselves as a people irrespective of our geographical barriers.

The unfortunate irony of this school of thoughts is that, Gender has always been grounded in a traditionally binary concept and is therefore limited by that binary in its deliberations and discussion in the form of she/he pronouns. Gender is not different from sex assigned at birth which may be designated with categories such

as female or male. We also take cognizance of the fact that a person's gender is expressed outwardly through their name, clothing, haircut, behaviour, voice, phonetic expression or body characteristics.

SOCIAL TIES

The earliest and often the strongest and most lasting social ties experienced by people everywhere are the family through marriage. The institution of marriage is an ordinance for the preservation of the world of mankind.

It is a new and culturally peculiar idea that human sexuality is all about intimacy and pleasure, but not necessarily babies. Babies and reproduction matter; and sure, while not every male/female sexual engagement is toward the end of procreation – intimacy and pleasure matter as well – it has been the overwhelming norm and desire in nearly all marital relationship through time. Indeed, to establish a sexual relationship without any interest in or openness to babies is contrary to God's intention and sometimes frowned at by our society.

We need to realize that every person ever born can trace their origin to a mother and a father. There is no exception, including those artificially produced.

In all societies, the child learns values and skills which have to be handed on, if the culture and social order is to continue, and the immediate family has a role to play in this. It has been observed that, in some societies, marriage is not only concerned with birth, protection and education of children, but it is also a means of creating alliances between groups of people and of specifying who should inherit certain rights, goods and authority. Thus, marriage, the family and the systems by which people trace their descent play a vital role in social, political and economic organization.

SAME-SEX MARRIAGE

Our society today, is witnessing the introduction of another form of marriage or union of the same sex or gender identity – Homosexuality and Lesbianism.

In most developed Countries, same-sex relationships are accepted, and are accorded legal protection. Many governments have established formal structures for confirming legal relationship (either as marriage or partners) between people of the same sex.

On the other hand in cultures influence by anti-gay religious dogma, homosexuality and Lesbianism are still considered, a perversion and has been outlawed. In some Muslim nations it remains a capital crime punishable by death.

WHAT THE BIBLE SAYS ABOUT SAME-SEX MARRIAGE

The Bible specifically calls same-sex (homosexuality) behaviour sin (Lev.18:22; Rom.1:18-32; 1Cor.6:9-11). In fact, it is called an *“enormous sin”*. We must note that same-sex love is against nature and is condemned by God. It is the underlining factor for the destruction of Sodom Gomorrah in the Scriptures (Gen 19:5).

Many homosexuals believe that their desires are normal and that they have a right to express them. But what one seems to forget is that God does not obligate nor encourage us to fulfill all our desires (even the normal ones). Those desires that violate his laws are wrong and are to be avoided without conditions.

CAUTION

We must be careful however, to condemn only the practice and not the people. Those who commit homosexual acts are not to be feared, ridiculed, or hated. They can be forgiven and their lives can be transformed like any other person who was once wandering in darkness prior to his receiving Christ’s gift of salvation.

CONCLUSION

The LBGTQI+ frowns on our cultural and Christian values. Nowhere in our history as a people has a nod or acceptance been given to other sexual union than between a man and woman. This has been the apparently uncontested historical teaching of Judaism, Islam and Christianity and it is not something these true religious bodies will be free to adjust with the times.

It is not mere traditionalism that makes sex distinct marriage the norm for our society. Rather, it is a common grace God has bestowed on us a people at all times that is rooted in deeper theological and cultural reasons. The Christian literature tells us that humanity is uniquely created to show forth the image of God in the world; to make visible the invisible. God does this not just in generic, androgynous humanity, but through two very perfect and similar but distinct types of humans; male and female. They are human universals and not cultural construct.

Every religious organization entreats its followers to obey its tenets. Undoubtedly, most of us would want to rewrite our religious tenets to make life easier. Religion is a demanding faith. Our teachings define and change us and not the other way around.

Our dear country has enjoyed a relative peace and all efforts need to be employed to sustain it. It must be emphasized that the prosperity and welfare of our country remains paramount and therefore, we all need the peace of God and peace of mind to bring our dreams to be fulfilled.

It is my desire that Christians and other faiths would be burdened to inculcate the duty of praying for the Nation: its peace; its unity; its prosperity; its increase; its influence on the world at large.

The prayer should not divide religious organization by schism or heresy but that its members may cherish for each other right feelings; that there may be no jealousies, no envying but rather regard and treat each other with kindness, respect and with mutual recognition; that the peace of God may attend us all and triumph in the Nation.

I pray that Parliament, as the accredited representatives of the good people of Ghana and coming from various cultural and religious backgrounds would be circumspect in the discourse on the Private Bill on the "Same-Sex" placed before them. The good people of Ghana have loudly and openly expressed their disgust on the issue as shameful, unethical and totally unacceptable in our society.

If posterity will one day examine the extent to which power given to a people group, such as Parliament, was exercised, then let the 'will' of the people prevail.

Long Live Ghana; Long Live Parliament.

